

IPBES VA Chapter 3. Historical development of nature-based valuation methods

Code: IPBES_VA_3.4

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Project Leader(s)

Tuyeni Heita Mwampamba (tuyeni@iies.unam.mx)

Researcher(s)

Houda Ghazi (ghazi.houda@yahoo.fr)

Marcello Hernández-Blanco (marcello.hernandez.b@gmail.com)

Data curator(s)

Victoria Contreras (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 3. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Ch. 3 that is to assess different valuation methodologies and approaches, including (a) biophysical, social and cultural, economic, health and holistic (including indigenous and local community-based) and (b) approaches for the integration of different types of values. To acknowledge the historical development of nature valuation methodologies to what it is today, a systematic review and the use of expert knowledge were used to provide evidence.

Process overview:

Protocol

Historical development of nature-based valuation methods

miro

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic review

Search languages: English

Search engine: Web of Science & Google Scholar

Exact search date: October 15, 2020

Sample extracted: Not determined

Fields extracted:

- Authors
- Category
- Title
- Year
- Abstract
- Source
- Publisher
- ArticleURL

Search terms:

```
TS= ("forest*"
      AND "valu*"
      AND "method*"
      AND "histor*"
      AND "review"
      AND "Silv*"
      AND "quanti*"
      AND "Assessment"
      AND "measure"
      AND "quatif"
      AND "historical"
      AND "developments"
      AND "valuation"
      AND "methods"
      AND "fisheries"
      AND "Aquatic"
      AND "Marine"
      AND "Ecosystem services"
      AND "Soil"
      AND "Agriculture"
      AND "Water"
```

Treatment applied (R1): Papers were screened out according to expert criteria, this included a review of abstracts, and the inclusion of topics: "genetics and micro-organism". Also, as the review was focused on the historical development no period was defined.

Sample extracted (B): 83 documents

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES_VA_3.4_Biophysical valuation history_(A)

Type of analysis/search/review: Expert knowledge

Contribution languages: English

Search Date: October 15, 2020

Sample size: 49 documents

Location and Format of the Data (B): IPBES_VA_3.4_Biophysical valuation history expert knowledge_(B)

Analysis of the Data: Papers were read to integrate historical aspects of valuing nature, results are presented across the chapter.

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description of file
A	IPBES_VA_3.4_Biophysical valuation history_(A)	.csv	53 KB	Sample extracted from the systematic review (83 documents)
B	IPBES_VA_3.4_Biophysical valuation history expert knowledge_(B)	.csv	7 KB	Sample obtained by expert knowledge (49 documents)